

Exploring liquid crystalline and gel phase of lipid vesicles via the photophysics of a 4'-(diethylamino)-3-hydroxyflavone dye

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Abstract : Hydration and fluidity of the liquid crystalline and gel phase were investigated by studying the photophysics of a fluorescent dye, *N*-[[4'-*N,N*-diethylamino-3-hydroxy-6-flavonyl]methyl]-*N*-methyl-*N*-(3-sulfopropyl)-1-dodecanaminium, inner salt (F2N12S), incorporated into phospholipid unilamellar vesicles. A unique feature of both an excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) and a dynamic Stokes shift associated with solvent relaxation is demonstrated in the photophysics of F2N12S. Whereas the ESIPT dynamics is faster in the gel phase than the liquid crystalline phase, solvent relaxation is slower in the gel phase (average relaxation time ~ 1.35 ns) than the liquid crystalline phase (average relaxation time ~ 1.00 ns). This opposite trend of variation in the ESIPT and solvent relaxation dynamics indicates to the weaker hydration and lower fluidity of the gel phase than the liquid crystalline phase of lipid vesicles.

Keywords : ESIPT, solvent relaxation, TRES, TRANES, hydration parameter.

Introduction

Phospholipid bilayers mimic closely the cell membranes. Water has a key role in the formation and maintenance of the cell membrane architecture, and its functioning¹. The lipid bilayer of the cell membranes contains water molecules within the lipid head-group region, and also between the fatty-acyl chains²⁻⁴. It is characterized by two fundamental physicochemical parameters, polarity and hydration, which exhibit a strong gradient across the bilayer⁵. Moreover, membrane fluidity has been shown to be closely related to membrane hydration⁶. The study of these physicochemical parameters in lipid bilayers is likely to aid us in understanding how the biological membranes function.

Polarity-sensitive fluorescent probes e.g. Prodan⁷⁻⁹ and Laurdan^{10,11} have been used so far to study hydration and polarity of the lipid bilayer. However, these probes have some limitations regarding the separate discrimination between polarity and hydration effects. Polarity describes the ability of the surrounding molecules to dielectrically stabilize the ground and the excited state dipoles of the fluorescent probes¹²⁻¹⁴. Hydration of the lipid bilayer also contributes to this dielectric stabilization, since water molecules form a highly polar environ-

ment. Water molecules may also engage in specific H-bonding interactions with fluorescent probes resulting in changes of intensity and shifts of emission peak maxima, used for the determination of polarity. Specific hydrogen bonding interaction between Prodan and protic solvent molecules was found to induce a red shift of ~ 50 nm, which is about half of its total solvatochromic response¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Thus, the "polarity" sensed by these probes, reflects the collective response of both the classical polarity^{12,13} and the hydrogen-bonding effects of the environment. In consequence, to obtain an unambiguous picture of polarity and hydration at precise location and orientation in the lipid bilayer, multi-parametric fluorescent dyes based on 3-hydroxyflavone were developed¹⁸⁻²¹. These 3-hydroxyflavone dyes display an excited state intramolecular proton transfer reaction (ESIPT) resulting in a dual fluorescence with two highly resolved emission bands (Scheme 1). The short-wavelength band corresponds to emission of the normal (N^*) excited state, while the long-wavelength band originates from the proton-transferred tautomer (T^*). The position of these bands as well as their relative intensities are highly sensitive to polarity and H-bonding effects, thus allowing the development of algorithms for discriminating between these two effects²².

Scheme 1. Excited State Intramolecular Proton Transfer of 4'-(dialkylamino)-3-hydroxyflavone, N* and T* are the excited normal and proton-transferred tautomers, respectively.

However, steady state fluorescence spectroscopy were used for most of the studies using 3-hydroxyflavone dyes, except our recent work²³ based on time resolved fluorescence measurements, which demonstrated an ESIPT coupled with solvent relaxation for the F2N12S dye (Fig. 1) in the liquid crystalline phases of EYPC and DOPC lipid vesicles. The ESIPT dynamics in these liquid crystalline phases were slightly different but the solvent relaxation occurred on a similar time scale of ~ 1 ns²³. As the hydration and fluidity of the liquid crystalline and gel phases of a lipid bilayer are different^{6,19}, time-resolved fluorescence measurements were carried out for the F2N12S dye in the liquid crystalline phase of dioleoyl phosphatidylcholine (DOPC) and the gel phase of (DPPC), respectively to monitor the hydration and fluidity of the lipid bilayers.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the ground-state species of F2N12S with respect to lipids in the bilayer.

Materials and methods :

The phospholipids 1,2-dioleoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DOPC) and 1,2-dipalmitoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DPPC) were from Sigma. The probe F2N12S was synthesized as described earlier²⁴. Large unilamellar vesicles (LUV) of 200 μ M lipid concentration were obtained in 15 mM phosphate-citrate buffer, pH 7.0, by the classical extrusion method.²⁵ LUVs were labeled by adding an aliquot of the dye stock solution in DMSO to a final concentration of 2 μ M. In LUVs labeled with the probe, DMSO was always $\leq 0.1\%$ v/v.

Absorption and fluorescence spectra were recorded at 20 °C on Cary 4 spectrophotometer (Varian) and FluoroMax 3.0 (Jobin Yvon, Horiba) spectrofluorometer, respectively. Time-resolved fluorescence measurements were performed with the time-correlated, single-photon counting technique using the frequency-doubled output of a Ti-sapphire laser at 427 nm (Tsunami, Spectra Physics) pumped by a Millennia X laser as discussed in details elsewhere²³. The full width at half-maximum of the instrument response function was ~ 40 ps. The time-resolved decays were analyzed together with instrument response functions using an iterative reconvolution method²⁶ which provided an effective time resolution of ~ 10 ps. The goodness of the fit was evaluated from the χ^2 values, the plots of the residuals and the autocorrelation function.

Time-resolved emission spectra (TRES) were generated from a set of emission decays (at least 16 wavelengths) recorded at 10 nm intervals spanning the fluorescence spectrum using the "Spectral Reconstruction" method as described elsewhere²⁷. The time evolution of the peak frequencies $\nu(t)$ in the TRES were fitted using a sum of two log-normal line shape functions :

$$F(\nu, t) = \sum_{i=1}^2 g_i \exp \left\{ -\ln 2 \left(\ln \left[1 + \frac{2b_i(\nu - \nu_i)/\Delta_i}{b_i} \right]^2 \right) \right\} \alpha > 1 \quad (1)$$

$$= 0, \text{ for } \alpha \leq 1 \text{ where } \alpha = \frac{2b_i(\nu - \nu_i)}{\Delta_i}$$

where g_i , ν_i , b_i and Δ_i are the peak height, peak frequency, asymmetry parameter and width parameter respectively. The FWHM (full width at half-maximum), $\Gamma(t)$ is related to the width and asymmetry parameter²⁷

and is extracted from log-normal fitting of the TRES. The solvation response or correlation function $C(t)$ was calculated according to :

$$C(t) = \frac{\nu(t) - \nu(\infty)}{\nu(0) - \nu(\infty)} \quad (2)$$

where $\nu(0)$ and $\nu(\infty)$ correspond to the peak frequency values obtained by "time-zero estimation" and infinity time, respectively.

The peak frequency at $t = 0$, which is not directly measurable, was calculated using the approximation proposed by Fee *et al.*²⁸

$$\nu(0) \approx \nu_{np}(em) - \nu_{np}(abs) + \nu_p(abs) \quad (3)$$

where the indices "np" and "p" refer to the steady-state peak frequencies measured in nonpolar and polar solvents, respectively, and the terms "em" and "abs" in the parentheses denote the steady state fluorescence and absorption peak frequencies respectively. Time-resolved area-normalized emission spectra (TRANES) were constructed by normalizing the area of each spectrum in TRES such that the area of the spectrum at time t is equal to the area of the spectrum at $t = 0$ ²⁹.

Results and discussion

Steady-state spectroscopy :

The steady state emission spectra of F2N12S display dual emission in the large unilamellar vesicles (LUVs) of DOPC and DPPC (Fig. 2A) with maxima at ~ 510 – 520 nm and ~ 570 – 580 nm, respectively, similar to its closely related analogues F2N8³⁰ and 4'-(dimethylamino)-hydroxyflavone (F)¹⁸. Several features of the steady state emission spectra, namely, the shape and position of the short-wavelength emission band, and its limited separation (~ 50 – 60 nm) from the T* band are noteworthy when compared between DOPC and DPPC and offer insights with regards to the hydration and polarity of the lipid bilayers.

The short-wavelength emission band (Fig. 2A) of F2N12S in DOPC and DPPC at ~ 510 – 520 nm is similar to the broad spectral profile of the short-wavelength band of analogous fluorescent dyes F2N8 and F in lipid bilayers^{18,30} and may be assigned to the superposition¹⁸ of the N* and H-N* bands (Fig. 3) corresponding to an emission of the H-bond free and H-bonded forms, respec-

tively (Fig. 1). In the H-bond free form (N) of F2N12S, there exists an intramolecular hydrogen bond between the 4-carbonyl and the 3-hydroxy moieties, whereas in the H-bonded form (H-N) an intermolecular hydrogen bond between the 4-carbonyl oxygen and water prevails without any intramolecular H-bond. On the other hand, the long-wavelength emission band at ~ 570 – 580 nm may be attributed to the proton-transferred T* form (Scheme 1). The H-N* band at ~ 540 nm, obtained from a decomposition of the fluorescence spectra (Fig. 3), originates from the intermolecularly H-bonded form of the dye. Moreover, the excitation spectra of F2N12S at the blue edge (470 nm) of the short-wavelength emission band is identical to that of the T* band at 575 nm, and is blue shifted by ~ 3 nm (Fig. 2B) from the excitation spectra monitored at the red edge (540 nm) of the short-wavelength band. This shift confirms the presence of two ground state species in lipid bilayers, namely, the H-bond free (N) form responsible for the N* and T* emission bands (Scheme 1) and H-bonded form (H-N) with a red shifted absorption which led to the H-N* emission around 540-

Fig. 2. Steady state emission (A) and excitation (B) spectra of F2N12S. Excitation spectra (B) are in DOPC vesicles. Excitation wavelength was 420 nm. "Spectra in DOPC are reprinted with permission from Ref. 23 Copyright {2012} American Chemical Society".

Fig. 3. Steady-state emission spectrum (dashed curve) in DOPC and its deconvolution into three component bands (solid curves).

550 nm (Fig. 3)²¹.

The short and long-wavelength emission bands, undergo an appreciable red and blue shifts of ~ 10 nm and ~ 7 nm, respectively, in going from the gel phase of DPPC to the liquid crystalline phase of DOPC (Fig. 2A). The origin of the red shift of the short-wavelength emission band in DOPC compared to DPPC may be reasonably explained on the basis of the deconvolution of the steady state emission spectra. The emission maximum of the deconvoluted N* band, is found to be red shifted at ~ 498 nm in the lipid vesicles of DOPC compared to its position at ~ 490 nm in DPPC, whereas, the shift of the deconvoluted H-N* band between these two vesicles is negligibly small at ~ 2 nm. As a consequence, the red shift of the short-wavelength emission band or the N* band is likely to originate from a difference in polarity of these large unilamellar vesicles, because the gel phase of DPPC offers a less polar microenvironment than the liquid crystalline phase of DOPC vesicles due to the lack of hydration¹⁹. The H-bond free form (N) is much more

polar in the excited state than the ground state ($\mu_{N^*} \gg \mu_N$) owing to a significant charge delocalization (Scheme 1) and thus is more stabilized relative to the ground state in the more polar DOPC vesicles than less polar DPPC, resulting in an appreciable red shift of the N* or the shorter wavelength emission band in the liquid crystalline phase relative to the gel phase. In addition, the response of the N* and T* states to intermolecular H-bonding with water molecules, is likely to be opposite owing to a selective stabilization of the N* state and destabilization of the T* state. The 4-carbonyl group of F2N12S possesses an effective negative charge in the N* state (Scheme 1), while in the T* state this negative charge is compensated by the transferred proton. Additionally, a significant charge separation is maintained in the ground tautomeric (T) state (Scheme 1). In consequence, the intermolecular H-bonding of negatively charged oxygen of the 4-carbonyl group with water molecules result in an effective stabilization of the N* state, whereas the T* state is destabilized by intermolecular H-bonding of water with 4-carbonyl group of the flavone dye, which is consistent with the observed red shift of the N* band and blue shift of the T* band in DOPC compared to DPPC. The opposite trend in shift of the N* and T* bands in the liquid crystalline phase of DOPC compared to DPPC, not only explains the smaller separation between the short-wavelength and the long-wavelength band (T*), but also indicates to the stronger hydration of the former than the latter. This is also consistent with the higher value of the relative hydration parameter^{18,19} of the DOPC vesicles than the DPPC vesicles (Table 1).

Time-resolved fluorescence spectroscopy :

The time-resolved fluorescence decays (Fig. 4) of F2N12S in lipid vesicles are strongly wavelength-dependent, and are fastest when monitored at the blue edge of

Table 1. Steady state photophysical parameters of F2N12S in large unilamellar vesicles

LUV	λ_{N^*} (nm)	λ_{T^*} (nm)	λ_{short} (nm)	$\lambda_{T^*} - \lambda_{\text{short}}$ (nm)	I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}	$I_{H-N^*}/(I_{N^*} + 0.4 \times I_{T^*})$
DOPC	498	578	522	56	0.95	0.80
DPPC	490	584	512	72	0.71	0.65

λ_{N^*} and λ_{T^*} are peak maxima of the deconvoluted N* and T* bands obtained from decomposition of the steady state spectra, λ_{short} is the peak maxima of the short-wavelength band, (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}) is ratio of intensities of the deconvoluted N* and T* bands, I_{H-N^*} is intensity of the deconvoluted H-N* band, $I_{H-N^*}/(I_{N^*} + 0.4 \times I_{T^*})$ is the relative hydration parameter^{18,19}.

Fig. 4. Time-resolved fluorescence decays of F2N12S in DPPC and DOPC lipid vesicles. Dashed (---) and solid (—) curves represent raw and fitted decay traces. Excitation wavelength is 427 nm. "Decay profile in DOPC is reprinted with permission from Ref. 23 Copyright {2012} American Chemical Society".

the steady state emission spectra at ~ 450 – 460 nm, and slowest at the red edge (~ 600 nm and above) of the T* band.

Further, several noteworthy features of the photophysics of F2N12S in DOPC and DPPC are manifested from the time-resolved fluorescence study.

The decays monitored at all of the emission wavelengths spanning the steady-state spectrum (~ 460 – 610 nm) are multiexponential with 3–4 components. A fast decay component (τ_1) of ~ 16 – 33 ps with a significant amplitude is observed at the blue edge (460 nm) of the N* band, whereas an identical rise component of ~ 17 – 35 ps is systematically observed with a negative amplitude (Table 2) at ~ 580 – 590 nm corresponding to the ESIPT tautomer (T*). Thus, the rise of the tautomer emission, within experimental error, correlates well with the decay dynamics of the normal (N*) species, which indicates to a precursor-successor type of relationship between the N* and T* forms, thereby, confirming the occurrence of an ESIPT reaction, $N^* \rightarrow T$ (Scheme 1). The time-resolved emission decays at both ~ 460 and 590 nm also display an identical long-lived decay component (τ_4) of ~ 2.5 – 3 ns which likely corresponds to the decay time (radiative plus non-radiative decay) of the N* and T* forms. This longest decay component (τ_4) remains more or less fixed, but its amplitude increases upon going from the blue edge to the red edge of the monitored wavelength range. The two pre-exponential coefficients (α_1 and α_4), describing the rise and decay of the T* form at 590 nm are similar in magnitude but opposite in sign (Table 2), which is consistent with the model of a reversible ESIPT reaction³¹. This is quite reasonable because the decay time of the ESIPT tautomer is roughly 100-fold

Table 2. Time-resolved fluorescence data of F2N12S (2 μ M) in LUVs (200 μ M, pH 7.0) at 20 $^{\circ}$ C

LUV	λ (nm)	τ_1	α_1	τ_2	α_2	τ_3	α_3	τ_4	α_4	χ^2
DPPC	460	0.016	0.780	0.107	0.160	0.564	0.040	2.73	0.020	1.01
	480	0.046	0.730	0.275	0.190	1.18	0.060	3.00	0.020	1.04
	510			0.133	0.530	0.73	0.260	2.86	0.210	1.14
	560	0.016	-0.550	0.120	-0.110	0.81	0.470	3.10	0.530	1.09
	590	0.017	-0.600	0.120	-0.190	0.68	0.400	3.14	0.600	1.20
DOPC	460	0.033	0.539	0.181	0.335	0.700	0.087	2.50	0.039	1.02
	480	0.058	0.371	0.265	0.335	0.795	0.150	2.63	0.144	1.01
	510			0.184	0.250	0.746	0.324	2.80	0.426	1.07
	540			0.220	-0.079	0.600	0.178	2.80	0.822	1.09
	590	0.035	-0.790	0.170	-0.210	1.00	0.160	2.70	0.840	1.20

τ_1 , τ_2 , τ_3 and τ_4 – decay times (ns), α_1 , α_2 , α_3 and α_4 – pre-exponential coefficients, χ^2 – goodness of the fit, obtained after deconvolution of the corresponding decay curves. The estimated error of the decay times is $< \pm 10\%$, λ is the emission wavelength for recording fluorescence decays. "Data in DOPC is reprinted with permission from Ref. 23 Copyright {2012} American Chemical Society".

larger than the fastest component attributed to ESIPT. In consequence, a fast equilibrium is established between the normal (N^*) and tautomer (T^*) excited states, in which the rates of both forward and reverse ESIPT are much faster than the decay (radiative plus nonradiative) rate for both states.

The fast decay component (τ_1) remains more or less constant at ~ 16 – 33 ps in the blue edge (~ 450 – 470 nm) of the N^* band, but increases in magnitude and decreases in amplitude on moving further towards the red with its complete disappearance in the range of ~ 510 – 550 nm. The increase of magnitude of the fast component (τ_1) at an wavelength of 480 nm and above and its complete disappearance (Table 2, Fig. 5) in the range of 510–550 nm suggests the occurrence of an additional decay channel, other than ESIPT for the deactivation of the N^* form. The time-resolved emission decays are also characterized

Fig. 5. Wavelength-dependence of amplitudes of the fluorescence decay times of F2N12S. "Data in DOPC is reprinted with permission from Ref. 23 Copyright {2012} American Chemical Society".

by another two decay components, τ_2 (~ 120 – 260 ps) and τ_3 (~ 0.7 – 1.2 ns) at all of the monitored wavelengths, but their amplitudes are wavelength-dependent. The shorter

component, τ_2 , which decays with a positive amplitude in the monitored wavelength range of 460–510 nm, evolves as a rise component at an wavelength of 540 nm and above (Fig. 5 and Table 2). The evolution of τ_2 as a rise component at 540–560 nm, where the emission is predominantly from the solvent relaxed $H-N^*$ species, indicates to an excited state process connected to the formation of the $H-N^*$ species from the N^* species. Following the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition the N^* species possesses a large dipole moment due to an intramolecular charge transfer (Fig. 1), which induces dipolar relaxation and a localized hydrogen-bonding interaction of a water molecule with the 4-carbonyl group of F2N12S leading to the formation of the $H-N^*$ species²³ in the lipid bilayer. This is quite likely, as the intramolecular charge transfer renders the 4-carbonyl group of a 4'-(dialkylamino)-3-hydroxyflavone dye, a strong H-bond acceptor in the excited state^{22,32}. The amplitude of the longer component (τ_3) is positive at all of the monitored wavelengths and is most pronounced in the range of 510–540 nm (Fig. 5), suggesting that this component likely describes the decay of the solvent relaxed $H-N^*$ species²³.

Time-resolved spectra : TRES and TRANES :

The temporal evolution of the emission spectra in TRES (Fig. 6) displays signatures, characteristic of both ESIPT and solvent relaxation in the photophysics of the F2N12S

Fig. 6. Time-resolved emission spectra (TRES) of F2N12S in LUVs at different delay times. TRES of DOPC is reprinted with permission from Ref. 23 Copyright {2012} American Chemical Society.

dye in the large unilamellar vesicles of DOPC and DPPC. ESIPT is manifested in the fast growth of the longer-wavelength emission band at $\sim 570\text{--}580\text{ nm}$ on a time scale of few hundreds of pico-seconds, whereas solvent relaxation is demonstrated by the time dependent Stokes shift of the short-wavelength band to the red on a nano-second time scale. The time-dependent Stokes shift of the N* band to the red associated with solvent relaxation, as well as the growth of the T* band which is ascribed to an ESIPT reaction become more clearly evident in the normalized spectral evolution of the TRES (Fig. 7). Furthermore, the time-resolved area normalized emission spectra (Fig. 8) reveals an isoemissive point at $\sim 520\text{ nm}$, which confirms the existence of a reversible two-state

Fig. 7. Normalized spectral evolution of TRES at different delay times for F2N12S in lipid vesicles. (Inset) shows different delay times after photoexcitation.

Fig. 8. Time-resolved area normalized emission spectra of F2N12S in lipid vesicles (at different delay times).

ESIPT kinetics between the N* and T* forms²⁹. All of these spectral features of the time-resolved spectra can be rationalized by the model of Das *et al.*²³, where (Scheme 2) it is hypothesized that apart from the population decay (radiative and non-radiative) two other decay channels, namely, a fast and reversible ESIPT ($N^* \leftrightarrow T^*$) and solvent relaxation ($N^* \rightarrow H-N^*$), compete for the deactivation of the hydrogen-bond free N* form in the S_1 state. The ground state heterogeneity, namely the presence of N (H-bond free) and H-N (H-bonded) forms^{18,21} in the ground state is also taken into account in this model²³ where photo-excitation of H-N provides an alternative radiative channel to the formation of H-N* species.

Kinetics of ESIPT and solvent relaxation in lipid bilayers :

At an early time (0.04 ns, Figs. 6 and 7) following

Scheme 2. Photophysical processes of F2N12S in lipid bilayers. H-N*, solvent-relaxed hydrogen-bonded normal form, N* - non-hydrogen bonded normal form, T*, ES IPT tautomer form. "Reprinted with permission from Ref. 23 Copyright {2012} American Chemical Society".

photoexcitation, the short-wavelength band is displayed at ~490 nm with the simultaneous appearance of a significantly weak T* band at ~570–580 nm. This demonstrates the formation of the proton-transferred tautomer (T*) from the N* form through ES IPT in a time of less than 40 ps because the short-wavelength band at ~490 nm is attributed to the H-bond free normal (N) form (Table 1, Fig. 1). TRES (Fig. 6) and TRANES (Fig. 8) also reveal that, at the later times (0.08–0.16 ns) the T* band grows in intensity at the expense of the N* band confirming further the formation of the T* form via an ES IPT transformation of the N* form. In addition, on a longer timescale (0.04–2.0 ns), the transformation of the N* species into H-N* species through solvent relaxation is observed resulting in a continuous time-dependent Stokes shift of the N* band to the red. The N* → H-N* transformation through solvent relaxation involves dielectric relaxation and a localized hydrogen-bonding interaction of a water molecule with the 4-carbonyl group of the F2N12S dye²³. Moreover, the manifestation of this dynamic Stokes shift over a much longer time window (0.04–2.0 ns) compared to the time scale (0.04–0.16 ns) for growth of the T* band, indicates to a distinctly slower kinetics of solvent relaxation than ES IPT.

ES IPT kinetics :

The demonstration of an identical decay or rise component (~16–35 ps) corresponding to the N* or T* forms at 460 or 590 nm, respectively (Table 2), provides us with a rough estimate of the ES IPT rate, $k_{\text{PT}} \approx (\tau_1^{\text{N}^*})^{-1}$ because both solvent relaxation and population decay (ra-

diative plus non-radiative process) compete with ES IPT for the deactivation of the N* form (Scheme 2). The ES IPT rate of F2N12S is approximated to be $6.25 \times 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $3.03 \times 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively, in the LUVs of DPPC and DOPC which correlates well with the ratio of intensities ($I_{\text{N}^*}/I_{\text{T}^*}$) of the N* and T* bands (Table 1), since a lower value of ($I_{\text{N}^*}/I_{\text{T}^*}$) implies a faster proton-transfer dynamics and vice-versa³³. The slower proton-transfer dynamics in the lipid vesicles of DOPC than DPPC may be attributed to a weakening of the intramolecular H-bond between the 3-hydroxy and the 4-carbonyl moieties of the N* form (Scheme 1), due to an intermolecular H-bonding interaction between the 4-carbonyl oxygen and water molecules³⁴. As a consequence, stronger hydration of the LUVs of DOPC than DPPC, induces a stronger intermolecular H-bonding perturbation of the intramolecular hydrogen bond in the H-bond free (N) form of F2N12S (Fig. 1) leading to a slower ES IPT dynamics, whereas weaker hydration of the LUVs in DPPC gives rise to a faster ES IPT dynamics. The slower ES IPT dynamics of the dye is reflective of a stronger hydration of the liquid crystalline phase of DOPC than the gel phase of DPPC, which also corroborates well with the relative 'hydration parameter' (Table 1) of the lipid vesicles.

Kinetics of solvent relaxation :

A continuous time dependent Stokes shift (TDSS) of the short-wavelength emission band to the red (Figs. 6 and 7) demonstrates solvent relaxation around the N* form in the lipid bilayer of LUVs. However, no such dynamic Stokes shift is observed for the long-wavelength emission band, suggesting the absence of solvent relaxation for the relatively less polar T* species. Time-dependent decay (Fig. 9) of the solvent correlation function, $C(t)$ gives quantitative information on the kinetics of solvent relaxation. The solvent correlation functions for DPPC and DOPC are satisfactorily fitted with a bi-exponential function :

$$C(t) = \{a_1 \exp(-t/\phi_1) + a_2 \exp(-t/\phi_2)\} \quad (4)$$

where a_1 , a_2 are the pre-exponential coefficients and ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 are the solvent relaxation time constants.

In the lipid vesicles, a bimodal decay of the solvent correlation function with a fast (150–230 ps), and a slow (1.7–2.1 ns) relaxation component is observed (Table 3). The average relaxation time of ~1.0 ns for the F2N12S

Fig. 9. Kinetics of solvent relaxation in DPPC and DOPC LUVs.

dye in the liquid crystalline phase of DOPC appears to be quite similar to that observed by Hof *et al.*³⁵ for PRODAN in the liquid crystalline phase of egg-phosphatidylcholine vesicles. However, the solvation response of the dye in the gel phase of DPPC occurs on a slower timescale (Fig. 9) with an average relaxation time of ~ 1.35 ns (Table 3). This mean relaxation times in the nanosecond time scale are much slower than solvent relaxation in pure water and was attributed to a time dependent reorientation of the molecular domains of phospholipids and

Table 3. Decay components in the solvent relaxation of F2N12S in LUV

LUV	ϕ_1 (ns)	a_1	ϕ_2 (ns)	a_2	$\langle \tau_s \rangle$ (ns)	$\Delta\nu$ (cm^{-1})
DPPC	0.233	0.40	2.10	0.60	1.35	1833
DOPC	0.151	0.43	1.70	0.57	1.03	2267

$\langle \tau_s \rangle = \int_0^{\infty} C(t) dt$ = average solvent relaxation time. $\phi_1, \phi_2 =$ solvent relaxation components, a_1 and a_2 are the corresponding pre-exponential coefficients, $\Delta\nu$ is the dynamic Stokes shift as discussed in details in the experimental section. "Data in DOPC is reprinted with permission from Ref. 23 Copyright {2012} American Chemical Society".

water molecules surrounding the fluorescent dye^{36,37}. The average relaxation time decreases on going from DPPC to DOPC with an increase in the dynamic Stokes shift ($\Delta\nu$, Table 5). As the time-dependent Stokes shift depends on the solvent polarity and the change in the solute's dipole moment³⁵, and because the same F2N12S dye has

been used in both of the vesicles, the difference of $\Delta\nu$ directly reflects microenvironments of different polarity. So, the higher dynamic Stokes shift (Table 3) in DOPC than DPPC indicates to the higher polarity of the liquid crystalline phase of DOPC than the gel phase of DPPC, owing to a much less hydrated microenvironment of the gel phase than the liquid crystalline phase¹⁹. Thus, there are less number of relaxing water molecules in the gel phase of DPPC than the liquid crystalline phase of DOPC, to cause a slower collective response of the molecular domains of phospholipids and water molecules in the former than the latter which gives rise to the slower average relaxation time of the dye in DPPC than DOPC. Furthermore, the slower collective response of the dye environment may be due to its higher microviscosity and vice-versa. As a consequence, the higher average relaxation time (~ 1.35 ns) of the F2N12S dye in the lipid vesicles of DPPC than that (~ 1 ns) in DOPC, indicates to a higher microviscosity and lower fluidity of the gel phase than the liquid crystalline phase¹⁹.

Conclusions :

TRES and TRANES, demonstrate the existence of both ESIPT and solvent relaxation in the photophysics of the F2N12S dye in large unilamellar vesicles (LUVs). The dynamics of ESIPT is faster in the gel phase of LUVs composed of DPPC than the liquid crystalline phase of DOPC vesicles, whereas solvent relaxation is slower in the former when compared to the latter. The opposite trend in variation of the ESIPT and solvent relaxation dynamics reveals weaker hydration, and lower fluidity or higher microviscosity of the gel phase of DPPC than the liquid crystalline phase of DOPC.

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